

Physical model tests of clay-rich submarine landslides and resulting impact forces on offshore foundations

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Prof. A.I. Incecik

Keywords:

Submarine landslides
Physical model testing
Impact forces
Run-out distance

ABSTRACT

Experimental model tests on submarine landslides have been conducted to quantify complete slide events and to determine impact forces on a foundation pillar for clay-rich submarine landslide events on steep slopes. In total, 21 experiments were conducted, where the differences between the experiments were bed inclination and soil properties. All experiments were performed with kaolin clay, where water contents and consolidation time were varied. Each model test was triggered by rapidly increasing the bed inclination of a box containing the slide material. The model tests started as a nearshore slope failure, where the water elevation was aligned with the initial top elevation of the debris material and continued as submarine landslides. The model tests were supplemented with a laboratory testing program, to determine the geotechnical and rheological properties for the soil used in the model tests. The flow mechanism for all experiments indicates a hydro-planning mechanism, with limited contact between the bed and the sliding flow. The results from the model tests have been applied to a field event, based on similitude laws. The normalized results can be applied to estimate the flow envelope for all clay-rich submarine landslides, where undrained conditions apply during the flow event.

1. Introduction

Submarine landslides pose hazard to offshore and nearshore infrastructures, including oil- and gas facilities, pipelines, offshore wind turbines and bridge foundations. Submarine landslides can induce huge impact forces on the infrastructure and entrain the seabed (Hampton et al., 1996; Locat and Lee, 2002; Puzrun, 2016). In addition, submarine landslides may generate tsunamis, which may cause significant damage on nearshore facilities (Harbitz et al., 2004). Compared to onshore landslide, submarine landslides tend to be larger and have larger run-out distances (Edgers and Karlsrud, 1982). Geologic environments which are prone to submarine landslides include fjords, active river deltas, submarine canyons, open continental margins and at oceanic volcanoes and ridges (Hampton et al., 1996). Common triggering factors include earthquakes, wave loading, tides, rapid sedimentation, erosion, shallow gas release, glaciation and human activities (Locat and Lee, 2002). The different triggering factors reduces the initial slope stability either or both by increasing the shear stresses in the slope and by reducing the soil strength. The morphology of detected submarine landslides can be

evaluated based on combined geophysical and geotechnical investigations, where detailed bathymetry, seismic profiles and soil sampling can be used to characterize the slide event by means of scar and deposit area, run-out distance and soil characteristics (Clare et al., 2018). Important aspects of the events will however remain uncertain, with flow velocity and flow mechanism as examples. Few direct observations of submarine landslide events exist. The flow velocity of the 1929 Grand Banks event was determined from subsequent telecommunication cable failures (Heezen and Ewing, 1952). In some cases, submarine landslides have caused failures of offshore structures, e.g. the hurricane Camilla event in 1969 in the Gulf of Mexico initiated a major submarine landslide event due to the waves, which caused collapses of three jacket structures (Bea et al., 1983). As few direct observations of the events exist, physical model testing on submarine landslides is an important approach to examine the flow response (De Blasio et al., 2004; Elverhøi et al., 2005, 2010). The physical model tests presented herein, focus on steep clay-rich submarine landslides, which are typically observed in fjords. The model tests serve two purposes.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2023.113966>

Received 26 December 2022; Received in revised form 3 February 2023; Accepted 12 February 2023

Available online 19 February 2023

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- To improve the understanding of the mechanics of clay-rich submarine landslides occurring at steep fjord flanks and the resulting slide impact on seabed structures.
- To provide test data that can serve as a validation for numerical models.

2. Summary of earlier works

A short outline of the most relevant previous conducted model tests on submarine landslides is presented herein.

Mohrig et al. (1998) examined flow mechanisms of submarine landslides using quartz mineral with no clay content. The experiments included both subaerial and submarine conditions, with bed angles ranging between 1 and 20°. The model tests identified flow mechanisms of hydro-planning, involving a basal lift of the flow head and turbidity current generation. A criterion for hydro-planning was proposed based on a densimetric Froude number Fr_d (eq. (1)), with initiation to hydro-planning equal to 0.4. The variables in eq. (1) include the head velocity, U , the density difference between soil and water, $\Delta\rho=(\rho_{soil}-\rho_{water})$, the flow height, H , and the bed inclination, β . Although the turbidity current mechanism was identified in the experiments, less than 1% of the total release mass eroded from the high-density flow during the experiments.

$$Fr_d = \frac{U}{\sqrt{\frac{\Delta\rho}{\rho_{water}} g \cdot H \cdot \cos(\beta)}} \quad (1)$$

Mohrig et al. (1999) carried out experiments of slurry mixtures of kaolin clay and quartz mineral. The model tests included both subaerial and submarine conditions, and they investigated both a rough and a soft bed. The soft bed consisted of deposits from previous experiments. The inclination of the main section of the bed was 6° for all experiments. The study presented run-out distances and flow head velocity profiles. The run-out distance of the submarine experiments was larger than for the subaerial experiments. The results from the submarine landslide experiments showed very similar velocity profiles and run-out distances for the hard and the soft beds. The model tests were extended in Marr et al. (2001) and Mohrig and Marr (2003), aiming to examine the development of the low-density turbidity layer. A normalized parameter was introduced, τ_y/p_f , representing the ratio between the shear strength of the debris material and the frontal hydrodynamic stagnation pressure, as shown in eq. (2). The study introduced the definition “coherence” as a description of erosion, breakup, and turbulent mixing. The criterion between strongly coherent to weakly coherent flow was $\tau_y/p_f = 0.2$ based on the performed experiments.

$$\frac{\tau_y}{p_f} = \frac{\tau_y}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_{water} \cdot U^2} \quad (2)$$

Iltstad et al. (2004a, 2004b) performed experiments with varying the clay/sand ratio. The shear strength of the debris material was estimated with viscometer tests. The flow regimes were evaluated with coupled total stress and pore pressure sensors on the bed. The sensor data was used to define the mechanisms hydro-planning, fluidized flow, and grains in contact with bed. In the case of hydro-planning, the total stress and the pore-pressure were equal due to a basal lift of the flow. Fluidized flows also have equal values for total-stress and pore-pressure, but with larger variations in readings, indicating liquefied debris with grain collisions. Fluidized flow was observed for the flow heads with low clay content. The last mechanism, particles in contact with bed, represents the condition where the flow is sliding with bed contact. In this case measurements provided lower pore-pressure values than total stress values. Particle tracking was also performed at selected sections, to quantify the flow mechanisms for the different compositions. The work was supplemented with an un-confined experiment in Iltstad et al. (2004c), where the debris material was free to flow in the transverse direction of the bed inclination. This experiment showed a slide

mechanism with slide detachments and formation of outrunner blocks. Breien et al. (2010) used the same model test setup as Iltstad et al. (2004a, 2004b) to perform PIV analyses on sand-rich flows, and to investigate the sedimentary process of turbidite layers.

Zakeri et al. (2008) investigated impact forces on both suspended pipeline and pipeline in contact with the seabed. The water content was about 54% for all experiments, with a varying ratio between clay and sand. The impact forces were normalized by eq. (3) and eq. (4), where the $Re_{non-newtonian}$ represent the ratio between inertia forces ($\rho_{soil} \cdot U^2$) and the internal shear strength (τ_y) of the debris material. The C_d coefficient is the ratio between the impact pressure (q) and the inertia forces ($\rho_{soil} \cdot U^2$). The best fit and proposed design envelopes for the impact forces were presented for both the suspended pipeline and the pipeline in contact with bed.

$$Re_{non-newtonian} = \frac{\rho_{soil} \cdot U^2}{\tau_y} \quad (3)$$

$$C_d = \frac{q}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_{soil} \cdot U^2} \quad (4)$$

Liu et al. (2020) combined flume experiments with numerical CFD analyses. The study investigated the effect on the ratio between clay and sand on the flow and depositional mechanisms of submarine debris flows.

All the model tests above were triggered by an opening gate from a supply tank, where remoulded slurry was supplied to the flume.

Wang et al. (2018a, 2018b) investigated the flow mechanism of sand-rich flows using a model test setup with a submerged circular flume inside a rotating wheel. With the setup, the bed velocity is controlled, providing a relative flow velocity between the bed and the flow. Flow mechanisms and impact forces on a cable were examined.

Submarine landslides have also been modelled by centrifuge testing. Gue (2012) used a drum centrifuge to compare the response from released kaolin slurry with different g-levels, to investigate the applicability of the scaling laws on submarine landslides in the centrifuge. Acosta et al. (2017) used beam centrifuge to observe hydro-planning for different volume fractions of clay, sand and water. All model tests were initiated by release to remoulded slurry from a release box. Takahashi et al. (2020) investigated sand-rich submarine landslides using a beam centrifuge, with focus on initiation and transition to flow. The landslides were triggered by seismic loading, causing liquefaction of the prepared slopes.

3. Motivation

The Norwegian parliament has a long-term goal to replace several ferry crossings, in Western part of Norway, with an improved and continuous coastal highway route. In one of the projects, referred to as the Hordfast project (www.hordfast.no), a floating bridge moored to anchors on the seabed will cross the 5 km wide and 570 m deep fjord Bjørnafjorden. Previous submarine slides have been mapped at Bjørnafjorden (NPRA, 2017; Solli et al., 2017; Charlton et al., 2019). The soil conditions in the fjord are characterized with soft normally consolidated clays, also located at the steep flanks of the fjord. With these conditions, possible future landslide events, that could impact the anchors, are relevant in the project (NPRA, 2017). Understanding submarine landslides and their mechanisms are essential to account for possible future landslides in design, including the impact scenario with a foundation.

Physical model tests have increased the understanding of submarine landslides significantly, where flow mechanisms like hydro-planning, fluidized flow and transition to turbidity currents have been examined (Elverhøi et al., 2005, 2010). Some key features are however not addressed adequately in previous studies considering the work presented in this paper. For example, previous studies did not cover clay-rich flows on steep flanks as most of the previous model tests have

been performed on bed inclinations of 6° or less. Mohrig et al. (1998) experimented with varying bed inclination up to 20° , however these experiments were performed without any clay content. It is only Mohrig et al. (1999) that used model tests to investigate the submarine landslide run-out distance. In addition, there are no tests in literature that considered simulating impact forces on foundation pillar resulting from submarine landslides. The triggering method in the presented experiments, except from the sand-rich model tests in Takahashi et al. (2020), was an opening gate mechanism from a release chamber. In most cases this triggering method results in uncertain debris volume and discharge, which is required input in numerical back-calculations. The soil properties in most of the previous conducted experiments were either measured only by viscometer tests or estimated by empirical correlations.

The aim of the model tests presented herein, is to investigate the complete slide events for clay-rich submarine landslides on steep slopes. The experiments consider both run-out distance and impact forces on a foundation pillar. The experiments have been performed with well-controlled conditions to enable benchmarking for numerical simulations. The model tests are supplemented with a detailed laboratory test program to determine geotechnical and rheological parameters.

4. Physical model tests

4.1. Experimental set-up

The experiments were performed in the hydraulic laboratory at NTNU in Trondheim, Norway. An internal flume, 0.3 m wide and 10 m long, was inserted inside a larger tank, as showed in Fig. 2. A schematic illustration of the model test setup, including the instrumentation, is shown in Fig. 1. The flume was instrumented with six pore-pressure sensors, one wave sensor, four cameras, in addition to one load cell for the impact force measurements. The pore-pressure sensors were positioned at a dry panel outside the flume, with tubes connecting a filter in the flume bed to the sensor panel. The logging frequency of the sensors was 1000 Hz, while the cameras were operating at 100 frames per second. The flume consisted of three sections, where different inclinations could be adopted. Two main configurations were used, where the inclination of the run-out section was 12° and 18° . The model tests were performed to investigate either run-out distance or impact force on the foundation pillar. The impact pillar consisted of a solid PVC cylinder, which was fixed to a load cell at the rear side, while the load cell was fixed to the bed. The pillar diameter and height were 54 mm and 200

mm, respectively. A gap of 2 mm between the pillar and the bed was used to ensure that the impact loads were transferred through the load cell. The load cell was calibrated prior to the experiments, which included the effect on eccentric loading. A schematic illustration of the impact force configuration is shown also in Fig. 1. For both setups, the tilt of the soil release box was rapidly increased from 0 to 35° . The flume bed consisted of a material with a roughness of 50 μm .

4.2. Sample preparation and model test procedure

A soil slurry was first made by adding de-aired water to dry kaolin powder. The slurry became homogeneous using a concrete mixer device. A concrete vibrator was used to further limit the air content. Saturation degrees (S_r) of above 99.5% were derived from B-values from triaxial tests, indicating nearly fully saturated soil samples.

The soil slurry with desired water content was then inserted into a soil box, with a preinstalled mould, to maintain an approximate shape of the initial soil geometry. The width of the soil box was 27 cm. A soil volume of 12 l was used for all experiments, with a maximum height of 10 cm, a total length of 50 cm. The model tests were performed either as remoulded soil or with a self-weight consolidation time of one day (24 h). In case of a waiting time of one day, the box was sealed to prevent evaporation. The box was then lifted into the flume, unsealed and the mould removed.

The execution of the experiment started by increasing the tilt of the slide mass box rapidly from zero to 35° inclination, using a clump weight. The time from zero to a tilted position was about 0.5 s.

4.3. Scaling factors and similitude laws

The scaling factor for the most important parameters for clay rich submarine landslides, including impact scenarios are given in Table 1. Table 2 show the obtained similitude of the most significant non-dimensional parameters, considering the scaling factors from Table 1. The obtained similitude requires a scaled soil strength, with the same scaling factor as the soil stress. The last parameter in Table 2 is a time factor for consolidation (eq. (5)), which may be used to evaluate the drainage conditions during the landslide event (Hutchinson, 1986). In eq. (5), T_f is a non-dimensional time factor, t is the time after triggering, and may be taken as the estimated time of the landslide event (Norem et al., 1990), d is the drainage path and c_v the consolidation coefficient.

$$T_f = \frac{t \cdot c_v}{d^2} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the physical model test set-up with 18-degree run-out section and impact force setup. Drawing made to scale. Cameras as placed in the window panel section of the flume.

Fig. 2. Left: Overview picture of dry tank, Right: Side view of the tank filled with water. The initial section and the run-out section visible from the window panel section of the tank.

Table 1
Scaling factors from prototype to model tests for 1g environment.

Quantity	Dimension	Scaling
Length	L	1/n
Area	L ²	1/n ²
Volume	L ³	1/n ³
Acceleration	LT ⁻²	1
Inclination	1	1
Mass density	ML ⁻³	1
Stress	ML ⁻¹ T ⁻²	1/n
Dynamic time	T	1/n ^{0.5}
Velocity	L/T	1/n ^{0.5}
Force	MLT ⁻²	1/n ³
Strain	1	1

Table 2
Maintained similitude of non-dimensional parameters from prototype to model test if parameters is scaled in accordance with Table 1. Parameters defined in given equations.

Parameter	Similitude
$F_{r,d}$ (eq. (1))	1
τ_y/p_f (eq. (2))	1
$Re_{non-Newtonian}$ (eq. (3))	1
Re_{water} (eq. (9))	1/n ^{1.5}
T_f (eq. (5))	n ^{1.5}

For the impact scenario, the most important non-dimensional parameter is the non-Newtonian Reynold number ($Re_{non-Newtonian}$). Similitude in this parameter gives equal ratio between the inertia forces and the forces related to internal shear resistance of the debris material. Other scaling considerations of the impact pillar include the geometrical aspect ratio between flow height and pillar diameter. Similitude in the aspect ratio will be maintained by scaling the dimensions in accordance with the length scale in Table 1.

It is seen from Table 2 that similitude can be obtained for the densimetric Froude number (Fr_d), the mobility ratio (τ/p_f) and for the non-Newtonian Reynold number ($Re_{non-Newtonian}$), however not for the Reynold number for the water (Re_{water}) and the time factor for consolidation (T_f). Further, the mass density of the soil will change somewhat if the soil strength is scaled with the scaling factor. The physical model tests will consider a range of parameters, rather than being fitted to one case only.

5. Soil properties

The material used in the experiments was kaolin clay, where the water contents and self-weight consolidation time of the soil was varied. Laboratory tests were performed to determine its geotechnical and rheological properties. The soil parameter testing program also included Bjørnafjorden clay.

5.1. Soil testing methods

To determine the geotechnical and rheological parameters during a submarine landslide event, the soil behaviour at the different stages of the event must be covered, from pre-failure conditions to a rapid moving flow condition. To realise this a soil investigation scheme was planned and implemented in this study. The soil strength and strain rate dependency were investigated with cyclic DSS tests, T-bar tests and viscometer tests. A short outline of the testing methods and test conditions used in this work is given in the following, including the index testing.

Cyclic DSS tests: The tests were performed and reported in accordance with ASTM D8296-19 and consisted of a consolidation phase followed by cyclic undrained shearing. The tests were performed with a vertical effective stress of 37 kPa for both the kaolin clay and the Bjørnafjorden clay, and represents the in-situ vertical effective stress for the Bjørnafjorden samples used. The tests were performed as strain controlled, using a cyclic strain amplitude of about $\Delta\gamma_{cy} = 15\%$. Three tests for both kaolin clay and Bjørnafjorden clay were performed, with cyclic periods of 1, 50 and 2500 s, which corresponds to average strain rates of 0.024%/s, 1.2%/s and 60%/s for the three periods used. The tests consisted of minimum 30 strain-controlled cycles, which were sufficient to reach the residual strength.

T-bar tests: The T-bar tests were performed with a bar diameter and a bar length of 4 mm and 40 mm respectively, while the rod diameter was 2.5 mm. The tests were performed and interpreted based on the procedure of White et al. (2010), where the measured net bar resistance is converted to an undrained shear strength. According to Ganesan and Bolton (2013), undrained conditions on the T-bar test can be assumed when the normalized penetration rate, $V=U \bullet D/c_v$, is larger than 20, where U is the velocity (penetration rate), D is the diameter and c_v the consolidation coefficient. The consolidation coefficient (c_v) for the kaolin clay was measured between 4 and 12 m²/yr, which corresponds to a minimum undrained penetration rate of about 0.6–1.9 mm/s. The reference shear strength from the T-bar tests was taken from the penetration rate of 3 mm/s, ensuring undrained conditions. Tests with different water contents were performed, and the penetration rate was varied between 3 and 50 mm/s. The T-bar tests were performed with a self-weight consolidation time of one day (24 h), which was the same consolidation time used for the model tests. Minimum 15 loading cycles were performed after the virgin penetration, which was found to be sufficient to reach the residual strength in the T-bar tests. The conversion factor between strain rate and penetration rate was taken as $\gamma_{rate} = U/D$, which is consistent with Sahdi et al. (2014a,b).

Viscometer tests: A co-axial viscometer was used (Bohlin 88BV), consisting of an inner and outer cylinder, filled with soil material in between. The inner cylinder rotates at a specified rotation speed, and measures the corresponding torque, which is converted to shear stress. The inner and outer cylinder had dimensions of 25 mm and 27.5 mm respectively, giving a 1.25 mm space between the cylinders.

Index tests: The index testing included water content, fall-cone testing, particle size distribution, particle density tests, permeability tests and soil saturation tests. The soil saturation was derived from the obtained B-value in a triaxial testing device.

5.2. Undrained shear strength and soil sensitivity

The undrained shear strength of kaolin clay was mainly determined from T-bar tests. Fig. 3 shows the interpreted shear strength from both the virgin penetration and following loading cycles with a water content of $w_c = 81\%$. Both the intact and the remoulded shear strength are relatively uniform with depth, which was also found for the other performed T-bar tests with other water contents. The strengths were extracted in the middle-depth of the cyclic loading steps. Fig. 4 shows the remoulded shear strengths interpreted from the T-bar tests for different water contents. A power function (eq. (6)) using the liquidity index (eq. (7)) is used to fit to the points to a curve. The best-fit coefficients were $A = 848$ Pa and $b = 2.67$, where the unit of the remoulded shear strength is in Pa. The soil sensitivity for one day of self-weight consolidation was between $S_t = 1.7\text{--}1.9$, with an average value of 1.75.

$$\tau_{rem} = A \bullet LI^{-b} \tag{6}$$

$$LI = \frac{w_c - PL}{I_p} \tag{7}$$

5.3. Undrained effective friction angle and cyclic degradation

The response in terms of strain-strain behaviour and effective stress path from the test using a cyclic period (T) of 2500 s is presented in Fig. 5, together with compilation plots of the three kaolin tests in terms of accumulated normalized pore-pressure parameter (r_u) defined as $r_u = \Delta u_p / \sigma_{v0}'$ and cyclic shear stress $\tau_{cy} = (\tau_{max} - \tau_{min}) / 2$ for each cycle. The interpreted friction angles from the DSS tests were between 29 and 34°, with increasing friction angle with increasing strain rate. Most of the reduction in shear strength was obtained after 10 cycles, where each cycle consisted of a cyclic strain amplitude of $\Delta\gamma_{cy} = 15\%$. The obtained soil sensitivity (S_t) varied between 3.8 and 5.3, with lower soil sensitivity for increasing strain rate. The larger sensitivity obtained from the DSS tests compared with the T-bar tests may be attributed to a different set-up time and different consolidation pressures. The normalized excess pore-pressure r_u -values were extracted after each cycle. Large r_u values exceeding 0.9 were observed for the tests using a cyclic period of 50 and 2500 s.

Fig. 3. Interpreted shear strength from T-bar tests for kaolin clay, with a penetration rate of 3 mm/s and water content of 81%.

Fig. 4. Remoulded shear strength as a function of liquidity index, LI. The power law function is of the form $\tau_{rem} = A \bullet LI^{-b}$. Dual x-axis showed, with both LI and water content w_c .

5.4. Strain rate dependency

The normalized strain rate dependency for both kaolin clay and Bjørnafjorden clay are shown in Fig. 6. The results are normalized in terms of the measured shear strength at a strain rate of $\dot{\gamma}_{rate} = 100\%/s$, and include the cyclic DSS tests, and the viscometer tests. Fig. 6 also includes a Herschel-Bulkley rheology curve (eq. (8)), containing the parameters that gave the best fitting to the data. It should be noted that a better curve fitting could be obtained considering specific water contents. The obtained Herschel-Bulkley parameters for both kaolin clay and Bjørnafjorden clay are included in Table 3. Comparing the strain rate dependency for the two materials, it is observed that the Bjørnafjorden clay had a larger strain rate dependency for strain rates less than 100%/s, while the strain rate dependency is larger for kaolin clay for strain rates larger than 100%/s. More details of the rheological tests are given in Sørli et al. (2022).

$$\frac{\tau}{\tau_{ref}} = \frac{\tau_0}{\tau_{ref}} \left(1 + k \left(\frac{\dot{\gamma}}{\dot{\gamma}_{ref}} \right)^n \right); \dot{\gamma}_{ref} = 100\% / s \tag{8}$$

5.5. Summary of material properties

The material properties of the kaolin soil for the water contents used in the model tests are summarized in Table 3. The table also includes soil index tests, which were either performed as a part of the testing program or extracted from NPRA (2017). It is seen from the table that the measured consistency indexes from the Bjørnafjorden clay is varying to a large degree; however, the tabulated values include the extremes for all boreholes and all depths. Most of the tests were around the mean value, although a layer with a lower plasticity index (I_p) was identified between 6 and 13 m below seabed.

6. Presentation of physical model test results

Table 4 presents key results from the 21 conducted experiments in the physical model. Fig. 7 shows the ratio between released mass to the total mass in the soil box (W_r/W_0) for the experiments as a function of water content and initial soil state. This parameter was determined by weight measurements of the soil box before and after the experiments. In general, larger released volumes were obtained for remoulded soil and increasing water contents. The pore-pressure and wave height measurements from a typical experiment (model test 11) are shown in Fig. 8. The processed data was processed using a running average of 0.05 s for both the pore-pressure and the wave height readings, to filter out noise. The velocity was determined from both the pore-pressure sensors and the cameras. Fig. 9 shows the steady velocity (v_{steady}) for each experiment, calculated from the arrival time and distance between the second

Fig. 5. Cyclic DSS data; Upper left: Shear strain vs shear stress for test with cyclic period $T = 2500s$, Upper right: Effective stress path, with effective normal stress vs horizontal shear stress for test with $T = 2500s$, Lower left: Pore-pressure ratio $r_u = \Delta u_p / \sigma_{v0}$ after each loading cycle for kaolin tests with $T = 1s$, 50s and 2500s, Lower right: Degradation curves for kaolin tests with cyclic period $T = 1s$, 50s and 2500s, with shear strength as a function of cycles with a stain magnitude of about $\Delta\gamma_{xy} = 15\%$.

Fig. 6. Normalized strain rate dependency for kaolin clay (upper plot) and Bjørnafjorden clay (lower plot). Plots include cyclic DSS tests, T-bar tests and viscometer tests. The results are normalized by the shear strength obtained at a strain rate of $\dot{\gamma}_{rate} = 100\%/s$.

Table 3
Summary soil properties obtained soil testing program.

Parameter	Kaolin clay	Bjørnafjorden clay
Clay (CC) and fine content (FC)	CC = 55%, FC = 100%	CC = 65%, FC = 98%*
Specific gravity (G_s)	$G_s = 2.73$	$G_s = 2.74$
Plastic limit	PL = 29%	PL = 17–34%, $PL_{average} = 30\%^*$
Liquid limit	LL = 58%	LL = 35–110%, $LL_{average} = 70\%^*$
Plasticity index	$I_p = 29\%$	$I_p = 18–74\%$, $I_{p,average} = 40\%^*$
Consolidation coefficient	4–12 $m^2/year$	0.6–6 $m^2/year^*$
Remoulded shear strength	40–200Pa, for $w_c = 110$ and 80%	1–10 kPa*
Friction angle from cyclic DSS, ϕ' (using $c' = 0$)	$\phi'_{slow} = 29^\circ$, $\phi'_{fast} = 34^\circ$	$\phi'_{slow} = 30^\circ$, $\phi'_{fast} = 35^\circ$
Soil sensitivity	$S_{t,1-day} = 1.7–1.9$, $S_{t,1-day,ave} = 1.75$	$S_{t,in-situ} = 2–11$, $S_{t,average} = 5^*$
Strain rate dependency (eq. (8))	$\tau_0 / \tau_{ref} = 0.65$, $k = 0.67$, $n = 0.30$	$\tau_0 / \tau_{ref} = 0.30$, $k = 2.33$, $n = 0.16$

For cells with *-symbol, values have been retrieved from NPRA (2017).

and the third pore-pressure sensor. The sensors were located on the run-out section, as shown in Fig. 1. The position of the flow head with time was determined from the different experiments using the video recording from the overview camera, with the software Tracker (physlets.org/tracker). The obtained results are shown in Fig. 10, while the corresponding velocities are showed in Fig. 11. The impact pillar was present in 18 of the 21 model tests. The measured maximum impact forces from the experiments with the impact pillar are shown in Fig. 12, while the impact force envelopes are shown in Fig. 13. In Fig. 13, the time has been shifted so that the maximum impact forces occur for the selected cases at the same time, i.e. $t = 2$ s. The impact forces were smoothed using a running average of $t = 0.02$ s. As the run-out distance was affected by the pillar, the run-out distances were measured only for the three model tests without an impact pillar. The flow height in Table 4 was determined 10 cm before the impact pillar and represents the maximum height of the flowing plug. The maximum thickness of the

Table 4
Overview and key results physical model test program.

Test no.	Test ID	w_c	W_r/W_0	v_{steady}	Q	L	H	$F_{r,d}$	τ_y/P_f
[–]	[–]	[%]	[%]	[m/s]	[N]	[cm]	[mm]	[–]	[–]
1	RO-18-Rem	105	94	0.65	–	168	120	1.32	0.29
2	Im-18-Rem	82	87	0.78	9.57	–	133	1.19	0.56
3	Im-18-Rem	85	89	0.66	10.72	–	144	0.95	0.68
4	Im-18-Rem	86	97	0.66	9.89	–	142	0.97	0.65
5	Im-18-Rem	110	94	0.71	3.85	–	127	1.40	0.20
6	RO-18-1dC	94	68	0.61	–	80	120	1.14	0.52
7	RO-18-1dC	100	68	0.59	–	80	120	1.16	0.42
8	Im-18-1dC	81	54	0.58	5.98	–	92	1.28	1.04
9	Im-18-1dC	85	68	0.61	8.67	–	146	0.87	0.78
10	Im-18-1dC	86	75	0.58	6.52	–	110	1.10	0.83
11	Im-18-1dC	91	76	0.64	6.65	–	121	1.16	0.54
12	Im-18-1dC	96	79	0.68	5.76	–	125	1.23	0.38
13	Im-18-1dC	103	88	0.64	5.27	–	133	1.14	0.33
14	Im-18-1dC	107	75	0.49	3.99	–	102	1.44	0.32
15	Im-18-1dC	113	88	0.70	4.22	–	124	1.44	0.19
16	Im-12-Rem	89	85	0.60	7.70	–	128	0.97	0.69
17	Im-12-Rem	95	93	0.56	4.86	–	110	1.11	0.59
18	Im-12-Rem	110	93	0.55	2.90	–	100	1.35	0.34
19	Im-12-1dC	99	85	0.54	3.51	–	93	1.30	0.55
20	Im-12-1dC	100	84	0.55	4.99	–	113	1.09	0.51
21	Im-12-1dC	109	80	0.50	4.30	–	100	1.33	0.35

Following abbreviations are used in the Objective-column: RO = Run-out, Im = Impact force, 12 and 18; tilt of run-out section in degrees, Rem = remoulded, 1 dC = 1-day consolidation. w_c = water content, W_r/W_0 = Mass release ratio, where W_r is the released mass a W_0 is the total initial mass, v_{steady} is velocity determined from arrival time from pore-pressure sensor 2 and 3. The column “Q or L” gives the impact force Q if the model test objective was impact or run-out length from start of the flat section for the run-out (RO) model tests. w_c is the water content of the debris material, the v_{steady} is obtained from arrival time and distance between pore-pressure sensor 2 and 3.

Fig. 7. Measure of released soil mass normalized by initial soil mass, as function of water content.

Fig. 8. Pore-pressure and wave height readings for model test 11.

flow was for most of the experiments larger than the initial thickness of 100 mm, with an average flow height of 120 mm. The calculated densimetric Froude number (eq. (1)) and the mobility ratio (eq. (2)) are included in Table 4, with range of $F_{r,d} = 0.87–1.44$ and $\tau_y/P_f = 0.20–1.04$.

Fig. 9. Steady velocity for the experimental tests; steady state velocity, derived from arrival time and distance between pore-pressure sensor 2 and 3.

Fig. 10. Flow head position with time after release.

Fig. 11. Average flow velocity for the 12-degree and the 18-degree setup, together with the flume inclinations for the two setups.

7. Evaluation of model test results

7.1. Flow mechanism

The flow mechanisms were observed from the cameras. All model tests showed a hydro-planning flow mechanism, and a turbidity current generation on the top of the flow head. The hydro-planning mechanism is consistent with the calculated densimetric Froude number (Fr_d)

between 0.87 and 1.44. Fig. 14 shows the flow mechanism for model test 1 at initiation and in the run-out section, and the landslide impacting with the pillar for test 14. The flow showed a chaotic flow pattern immediately after release, while a more uniform flow pattern is established in the run-out section of the flume. A distinct hydro-planning layer is present between the flume bed and the flow, and the flow head is up-bending. The low-density turbidity layer is well visible for the entire flow. The obtained mobility ratio (τ_y/p_f) from Table 4 suggest a

Fig. 12. Maximum measured Impact forces from experiments with impact pillar.

Fig. 13. Impact force envelopes for the experiments with impact pillar. Offset in x-axis is used to visualize the maximum force at the same instance.

strongly coherent flow according to Mohrig and Marr (2003). This was in line with the uniform flow pattern observed after the flow had entered the run-out section. Since the results show coherent flow, and due to the very low consolidation properties of the kaolin clay, the soil densities

and water contents are assumed constant during the experiments. Although the low-density turbidity layer was present for all experiments, the bulk part of the debris material remained in the high-density flow.

For most of the experiments, the flow envelope proceeded without any deposition before the deposit section of the flume. However, in a few of the model tests, the plug detached, where the flow head continued to flow, and the remaining slide deposited.

7.2. Pore-pressure measurements and wave heights

The pore-pressure readings were used to determine the flow velocity between each sensor, and in addition to serve as a general documentation of the experiments. As a hydro-planning mechanism involves limited contact between flow and bed, the pore-pressure values may be regarded as the hydrodynamic pressure associated with a flowing plug. The pressure values increase before the flow reaches the sensor position. A rapid increase is observed when the flow is located above the sensor position, while an under-pressure is present after the flow head has passed the sensors. The magnitude of the pore-pressures may be related to the theoretical stagnation pressure, $\Delta p_f = 1/2 \cdot \rho_{\text{water}} \cdot U^2$, which

Fig. 14. Flow mechanism and impact with pillar: Upper left: Test 1, immediately after triggering test 1 (taken from moving camera). Upper right: Test 1, flow head position 1.6 m and time 2.6 s after release box. Lower left: test 14, prior to pillar impact. Lower right: Test 14, during pillar impact.

applies for a steady state flow condition for the stagnant location. The measured pore-pressures in Fig. 8 is larger than the calculated stagnation pressure, which may be due to transient flow, interaction with the waves and other kinematic factors. The wave height sensor located between the first and the second pore-pressure sensor showed changes in the free water surface up to 36 mm, as observed in Fig. 8. When evaluating the pore-pressure readings, the pressure effects of the waves should be considered. The change in the pressure due to the wave is depending on wave height, water depth, wavelength, and the shape of the waves. Both the wave heights and the pore-pressure readings can benchmark to numerical analyses.

7.3. Flow velocity

The flow velocities have been obtained from both pore-pressure readings and from the camera recordings. The results have been compared, with similar results. The steady flow velocity presented in Fig. 9 shows slightly higher velocities for the 18-degree setup compared to the 12-degree setup, which is expected due to increased gravitational loads in the bed parallel direction. The flow velocities from the experiments show no dependency on the water content or soil state, although the difference in remoulded shear strength for the experiments has been larger than a factor of four. This supports the interpretation of a hydro-planing mechanism, with a limited contact between the flow and the bed, hence a low bed shear. Based on the assumption of negligible bed friction, the drag coefficient between the flow and the ambient water can be calculated from eq. (9), where the bed inclination (β), the effective submerged release mass per unit width ($W_{\text{submerged}}$), the maximum flow height (H) and the steady velocity ($U = v_{\text{steady}}$ in this context) are taken from Table 4. The obtained drag coefficients are shown in Fig. 15. The drag coefficients range between 1.4 and 2.5, with an average value of $C_{d,\text{water}} = 1.9$. The obtained drag coefficients show no dependency on the water content, which means that the drag coefficient is independent of the remoulded shear strength for performed experiments. However, as there is some degree of bed contact, the drag coefficient is likely to be slightly overestimated. The obtained drag coefficient of the flow may be linked to the Reynold number, given of eq. (10), where μ is the dynamic viscosity of the water. The Reynold numbers in the experiments ranged between $Re_{\text{water}} = 5 \cdot 10^4$ to $1 \cdot 10^5$.

$$C_{d,\text{water}} = \frac{2 \sin(\beta) \cdot W_{\text{submerged}}}{H \cdot \rho_{\text{water}} \cdot U^2} \quad (9)$$

$$Re_{\text{water}} = \frac{\rho_{\text{water}} \cdot U \cdot H}{\mu} \quad (10)$$

The velocities obtained from the video processing in Fig. 11 enable

further details of the flow process. For both the 12- and 18-degree setups, the flows obtain large initial velocities after release, and retards when the flow is entering the run-out section with lower inclinations. From visual observations, the flow shows a chaotic pattern in this stage, with large deformations within the plug and interaction with the wave above the sliding soil mass. The soil seems to be in contact with the bed in the region where there is a change in inclination. The velocities then increase as the flow pattern becomes more uniform, until the flow reaches a steady velocity. Local variations of the flow velocities are observed for the single events, which may be attributed to fluctuations in the bed contact and shape of the flow head, which leads to fluctuations in the bed friction and the hydrodynamic drag forces. Detachment of the plug will also give non-uniform velocity profiles.

7.4. Run out distance

The run-out distance for the three experiments investigating run-out distance is shown in Table 4, where the run-out distance is relative to beginning of the deposit section to the toe of the deposits. The run-out tests were performed using the 18-degree setup only. The run-out distance ranged between 80 and 168 cm, with longest run-out distance for the highest water content (test 1). The initial state of model test 1 was remoulded soil, while model test 6 and model test 7 was on 1-day consolidated soil. The thickness of the deposits from model test 1 was 3 cm only, while for model test 6 and model test 7 between 6 and 7 cm.

The run-out tests showed thin deposit from the beginning of the deposit section for all three experiments. This indicates at least a partly contact between bed and the flow, which further indicates that the hydro-planing mechanism was less prominent in this section. Using the simplified calculation method (eq. (11)) of Norem et al. (1990), the bed friction may be back-calculated as a fraction of the remoulded shear strength (eq. (12)). The method considers the change in kinetic energy between small sub-steps, due to bed friction (F), hydrodynamic forces (P) and gravitational loads (G). Following bed friction factors was obtained: $\alpha = 0.32$ for test 1, $\alpha = 0.33$ for test 6 and $\alpha = 0.39$ for test 7. The average friction coefficient was $\alpha = 0.35$. The back-calculations were done using an average value of the drag coefficient of $C_{d,\text{water}} = 1.9$, measured velocities and soil properties and specific release volume for each of the experiments. As the back-calculated bed frictions were significantly lower than the remoulded shear strengths, a partly hydro-planing or a water intrusion mechanism in this section seems likely.

$$\Delta E_k = \Delta \delta \cdot (F + P + G) \quad (11)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\tau_{\text{back-calc}}}{\tau_{\text{rem}}} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 15. Calculated drag coefficient of the flow (Re_{water}), assuming no bed friction, maximum flow height, submerged released mass.

7.5. Impact force on pillar

Typical impact force envelopes are shown in Fig. 13. The impact force is slowly increasing at low values prior to impact, where a sudden increase to the maximum force is observed. The time where the measured force was minimum 50% of the maximum force was measured between 0.4 and 0.5 s. The impact force shows a plateau with lower values for the next 1.0–1.5 s, which is related to the impact with the tail of the flow, as well as fluid drag. A small residual value is observed after the flow had passed the impact pillar, which is due to sticking of slide material to the impact pillar.

Fig. 16 presents the impact pressures normalized in terms of eq. (3) and eq. (4), where the measured resistance is represented in an equivalent drag coefficient. The data in Fig. 16 is obtained from test specific values given in Table 4, including flow height (H), flow velocity (v_{steady}), remoulded shear strength (τ_{rem}) and soil density (ρ_{soil}), in addition a rate factor of $N_{rate} = 1.35$. The normalization follows a convensional hydrodynamic normalization, with a Reynold equivalent number on the x-axis, and a drag coefficient on the y-axis. The impact forces seem to have a minor dependence on the initial soil state, where remoulded and self-weight consolidated soil of one day were considered. The trendline in Fig. 16 is obtained from a hybrid formulation given by eq. (13), which consist of a hydrodynamic term ($1/2\rho_{water}\bullet C_{d,hybrid}\bullet U^2$) and a geotechnical term ($N_{p,hybrid}\bullet N_{rate}\bullet \tau_{ref}$). The hybrid formulation was introduced by Randolph and White (2012), which re-calculated the experimental data on impact force on pipelines from Zakeri et al. (2008). The coefficients obtained from the experiments with impact pillar were as follows: $C_{d,hybrid} = 1.06$, $N_{p,hybrid} = 5.20$ and $N_{rate} = 1.35$. The rate dependency factor was obtained from the strain rate dependency parameters presented in Fig. 6, while the hybrid drag coefficient ($C_{d,hybrid}$) and hybrid resistance factor ($N_{p,hybrid}$) were determined in two steps. First, the best fit parameters were obtained ($C_{d,hybrid} = 0.98$, $N_{p,hybrid} = 4.80$), then the parameters were increased to represent a 95% confidence level in terms of statistical means. The statistical procedure was in accordance with DNV-RP-C207. Test 21 is the only test where the response deviates more than 20% to the best fit envelope. Camera observations indicate that this model test has limited internal plug shearing, which means that the material may have not been completely remoulded during pillar impact. This particular experiment is therefore regarded as an outlier.

$$q_{impact} = \frac{1}{2} C_{d,hybrid} \bullet \rho_{flow} \bullet U^2 + N_{p,hybrid} \bullet N_{rate} \bullet \tau_{ref} \tag{13}$$

Fig. 16 also include the best fit experimental data from Zakeri et al.

Fig. 16. Normalized impact forces, with the non-Newtonian Reynolds-number of the flow ($\rho\bullet U^2/\tau_{ref}$) on the x-axis and the drag-coefficient $C_d = q/(1/2\rho\bullet U^2)$ on the y-axis. The black-dotted line represents a hybrid formulation, with a drag coefficient $C_d = 1.06$, a bearing factor of $N = 5.20$, with strain rate coefficient $N_{rate} = 1.35$.

(2008) on a suspended pipeline and from Sahdi et al. (2014b) on rapid T-bar tests. It is observed that the experimental data on the suspended pipeline from Zakeri et al. (2008) is very similar to the obtained data on the pillar foundation, while the rapid T-bar tests from Sahdi et al. (2014b) show higher resistance. The flow mechanisms are somewhat different for the three cases; for both the landslide impacting with the pillar and on the suspended pipeline, a flow separation around the object is expected, while a deep T-bar test will show a flow-around mechanism, which gives a larger kinematic bearing factor of the T-bar tests. Further, the T-bar test and the suspended pipeline can effectively be regarded as plain strain conditions, while the aspect ratio between flow height and pillar diameter (H/D) is limited for the impact pillar experiments, with a variation between $H/D = 1.7$ and 2.8 for the performed experiments.

8. Applicability to field conditions

The model tests can provide insights to field events, especially if similitude of the most significant non-dimensional parameters is maintained. It was shown in section 4.3 that similitude can be obtained of the densimetric Froude number (Fr_d), the mobility ratio (τ_y/p_f) and the non-Newtonian Reynold number ($Re_{non-Newtonian}$), if the soil strength is scaled with the scaling factor between prototype and model test dimensions. The model tests were performed with a set of parameters, to investigate and obtain results for different conditions. The conversion of parameters from model test to prototype is shown in Table 5 using a

Table 5
Scaling factors from prototype to model test with $n = 100$, model test, prototype, and field parameters.

Quantity	Scaling	Model test	Prototype	Bjørnafjorden	Unit
L_0	1/n	0.5	50	50–500	m
H_0	1/n	0.1	10	10	m
$s_{u,ave}$	1/n	0.08–0.33	8–33	12.5*	kPa
$\tau_{rem,ave}$	1/n	0.045–0.19	4.5–19	2.5*	kPa
$\gamma_{soil,ave}$	1	14.0–15.0	14.0–15.0	15.5	kN/m ³
ρ_{water}	1	1000	1000	1025	kg/m ³
β_{flank}	1	12 & 18	12 & 18	10–30	degrees
β_{basin}	1	1.5	1.5	0.0–5.0	degrees
D	1/n	0.054	5.4	5–15	m

L_0 = Initial debris length, H_0 =Initial debris height, $s_{u,ave}$ = average intact shear strength over the debris height, $\tau_{rem,ave}$ = average remoulded shear strength over the debris height, β_{flank} = Inclination flank, β_{basin} = Inclination basin, D = Diameter foundation, soil permeability. Note: Different reference strain rate for Bjørnafjorden clay; From Table 3 follows an increase factor of appr. 2 by changing reference strain rate to 100%/s.

scaling factor of $n = 100$. Table 5 also includes the range of detected slide events with corresponding soil parameters at Bjørnafjorden, retrieved from NPRA (2017). It is seen from Table 5 that range in prototype parameters cover the Bjørnafjorden field events, where the prototype geometry is similar to one of the smaller detected slides at Bjørnafjorden.

By using the normalized results obtained from the model tests, the slide envelope of a possible future slide event can be estimated, including an impact scenario with a foundation pillar. The normalized results include the flow velocity (from $C_{d,water}$), the increase in the flow height (H/H_0), run-out distances (from $\alpha = \tau_{back-calc}/\tau_{rem}$) and impact forces (from $C_{d,hybrid}$, $N_{p,hybrid}$ and N_{rate}), where the obtained relationships were valid for all the conducted experiments. Table 6 show the estimated slide behaviour of a possible future slide event at Bjørnafjorden, considering an initial scar height and length of 10 m and 50 m, respectively, and slope inclinations of the flank and the basin of 18 and 1.5°, respectively. The calculation procedure to obtain the results are outlined below.

1. Determine the maximum flow height from the initial slide height and the obtained relationship between initial scar depth and maximum flow height.
2. Estimating the flow velocity using eq. (9), with a drag coefficient of the flow and the ambient water of $C_{d,water} = 1.9$.
3. Estimating the impact forces on a foundation pillar using eq. (13), with values in the hybrid formulation of $C_{d,hybrid} = 1.06$ and $N_{p,hybrid} = 5.20$. A remoulded shear strength of $\tau_{rem} = 5$ kPa (relative to $\gamma_{rate} = 100\%/s$) was considered. The strain rate factor (N_{rate}) is estimated to 1.05, by using the material specific Herschel-Bulkley parameters from Table 3, together the with estimated strain rate, using $\gamma_{rate} = U/D$.
4. Estimate the run-out distance, from start of basin to toe of slide deposits, from the procedure presented in section 7.4, with a bed friction of $\tau = \alpha \bullet \tau_{rem}$, using $\alpha = 0.35$.

The estimated run-out distance from the prototype may be compared with the field events. Charlton et al. (2019) presented the slide morphology of one of the detected slides at Bjørnafjorden. The topography and slide dimensions are not directly comparable with the prototype model considered, with both steeper flank (approximately 25°) and a larger scar length (about 100 m). The run-out distance was 350 m, which was, as expected, larger than the 280 m estimated from the prototype model.

Although the range of prototype parameters are within the Bjørnafjorden conditions, not all the similitude laws are satisfied. In particular, the Reynold number (Re_{water}) is about three orders of magnitudes below field conditions with a scaling factor of $n = 100$, as the velocity scales with the square root of the nominal scaling factor. The larger Reynold number in the field will influence the drag coefficient for the flow and the ambient water to some degree, which can be explored using CFD analyses. Further, similitude in the consolidation properties between model tests and field conditions are also not maintained, as shown in Table 2. However, the time factor for consolidation (eq. (5)) will for both the model tests and at field conditions be below $T_f = 10^{-3}$, which means that fully undrained conditions are expected for both conditions. If undrained conditions apply, the normalized results and the outlined calculation procedure can be applied on other conditions than for Bjørnafjorden, by considering specific conditions. The model tests have explored key aspects of clay-rich submarine landslides located at steep flanks and will serve as a validation for numerical analysis of submarine slides.

9. Conclusion

Model tests of clay-rich submarine landslide on steep flanks have been conducted. The experiments focused on flow mechanism and

Table 6

Estimated slide envelope for Bjørnafjorden, including impact with pillar foundation, based on findings from the model tests.

Parameter	Input parameter	Estimated results
Flow height (H)	$H/H_0 = 1.2$	$H = 12$ m
Flow velocity (U)	$C_{d,water} = 1.9$	$U = 8.5$ m/s
Impact pressure foundation (q)	$N_{p,hybrid} = 5.20$, $C_{d,hybrid} = 1.06$, $N_{rate} = 1.05^a$	$q = 90$ kPa
Run-out distance (L)	$\alpha = \tau_{bed}/\tau_{rem} = 0.35$	$L = 280$ m

The run-out distance is from start of basin to toe of debris deposits.

^a N_{rate} estimated from Herschel-Bulkley parameters in Table 3.

mobility, and impact forces on a foundation pillar. All model tests were conducted with kaolin clay, where water contents and consolidation time was varied. The model tests were supplemented with a laboratory testing program, to determine the geotechnical and rheological properties for the soil used in the model tests. The flow response was normalized in terms of flow velocity, run-out distance, and impact forces on a foundation pillar. A trendline for the impact forces on the foundation pillar was established based a hybrid geotechnical and hydrodynamic formulation. The estimated impact forces with the hybrid formulation corresponded very well with the measured impact forces for all water contents and soil states. The same formulation can be used to estimate the impact forces on foundation pillar and other cylindrical foundations in other conditions, by considering the specific soil conditions, including the strain rate dependency behaviour. The normalized results from the model tests have been adopted to a field scale, using the relevant scaling factors for the different parameters. The prototype model is similar to one of the smaller slide events detected at Bjørnafjorden, with most of the similitude laws maintained. The normalized results can be applied to estimate the flow envelope for clay-rich submarine landslides, where undrained conditions apply during the flow event. These well-controlled physical model tests enable validation of numerical tools that can be used to simulate submarine slides in the field.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Erik R. Sørli: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Lukas O. Hartnik:** Investigation, Data curation. **Quoc Anh Tran:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Gudmund R. Eiksund:** Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Vikas Thakur:** Funding acquisition, Supervision. **Heidi Kjennbakken:** Writing – review & editing. **Samson Degago:** Supervision, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

The work has been supported by the Norwegian Public Road Administration (NPRA), with both funding and fruitful technical advice. The support from the technicians at the geotechnical and hydraulic lab at NTNU has been highly appreciated. The cyclic DSS tests were performed at the NGI lab in Oslo.

Notation

A, b	Correlations between liquidity index and remoulded shear strength (eq. (7))
c', φ'	Effective cohesion and friction angle in Mohr-Coulomb criteria
CC, FC	Clay- and fine content
C_d	Drag coefficient
$C_{d,hybrid}, N_{p,hybrid}, N_{rate}$	Impact force coefficients in hybrid formulation (eq. (13))
c_v	Vertical consolidation coefficient
d	Drainage path
D	Pillar and bar diameter
DSS	Direct simple shear
F, P, G, $\Delta E_k, \Delta \delta$	Bed friction, hydro-dynamic force, gravitational force, change in kinetic energy and change in displacement in method of Norem et al. (1990).
Fr_d	Densiometric Froude number
g	Earth gravity
G_s	Specific gravity
H	Flow height
I_p, LI, PL, LL	Consistency indexes (Plasticity- and Liquidity index, Plastic- and Liquid limit)
L	Run-out distance
n	Scaling factor model test to prototype model
N_T	Correlation coefficient for T-bar test (eq. (6))
p_f	Stagnation pressure (eq. (2))
q_{net}	Corrected tip resistance
$Re_{non-Newtonian}$	Non-Newtonian Reynold number (eq. (3))
Re_{water}	Reynold number, with index “water” to distinguish from $Re_{non-Newtonian}$
r_u	Pore pressure ratio ($\Delta u/\sigma_{v0}'$)
S_r	Saturation degree
S_t	Soil sensitivity
s_u	Undrained shear strength
t	Time after triggering
T	Time period in a cyclic DSS test
T_f	Time factor for consolidation (eq. (5))
U	Flow velocity
v_{steady}	Steady flow velocity during submarine landslide experiments
w_c	Water content
W_r/W_0	Mass release ratio of the submarine landslide experiments
β	Bed inclination
γ_{rate}	Strain rate in shear
γ_{xy}	Shear strain in a cartesian xy-plane
Δu	Excess pore-pressure
$\Delta \gamma_{xy}$	Cyclic shear strain amplitude in the cartesian xy-plane during a cyclic DSS test
$\Delta \rho$	Density difference between submerged soil and water
ε_v	Vertical strain
ρ_{water}	Density water
σ_v	Vertical total stress
$\tau_0, k, n, \dot{\gamma}_{ref}$	Herschel-Bulkley parameters (eq. (9))
τ_{cy}	Cyclic shear stress amplitude
τ_{min}, τ_{max}	Minimum and maximum shear stress during a cycle of a cyclic soil test
τ_{rem}	Remoulded shear strength
τ_{xy}	Shear stress in a cartesian xy-plane
τ_y	Shear strength

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